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A disenchantment of legal concepts

Bartosz Brożek

- 1 Much ink has been spilled over the nature of legal concepts.¹ In this essay, I would like to spill some more, and it is up to the reader to decide whether I am justified in doing so. My goal will be to substantiate the thesis that legal concepts are not as important as is usually assumed. More precisely, I will venture to show that — given the abstract character of key legal concepts, such as legal personhood, ownership or guilt — there is no cognitive or theoretical advantage in investigating legal concepts *as such*. Rather, what one should be interested in are the *theories* within which these concepts appear. In other words, one will not get far and will not increase their understanding of the functioning of the law, by putting effort into *analysing legal concepts*; such an undertaking leads only to confusion. What one should do instead is to appraise, test, reject, or modify *theories* pertaining to legal issues, such as the theory of legal personhood, ownership, or guilt. When compared to such theories, legal concepts — if one insists that they do exist (which is a negligible problem) — are quite trivial.²

1 The grand illusion

- 2 An entry on concepts in the prestigious *Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy* has it that “concepts are the building blocks of thoughts. Consequently, they are crucial to such psychological processes as categorisation, inference, memory, learning, and decision-making. This much is relatively uncontroversial.”³ Thus, there is little doubt that concepts play a pivotal role in key mental processes. One cannot dispense with concepts when trying to understand or explain the nature of thinking in general, and consequently, also in legal thinking.
- 3 However, the same encyclopaedia entry, as well as many textbook accounts, admit that there is much controversy regarding our understanding of concepts. In particular, it is not easy to settle the dispute over the ontological status of concepts. They are depicted either as mental representations (i.e., mental images or word-like entities in a language of thought), abilities (i.e., dispositions of the organism to respond in a particular way to the encountered stimuli) or abstract objects (i.e., entities such as Fregean senses which

exist independently of the human mind, but somehow can be ‘grasped’). There is also an important and unsettled discussion pertaining to the structure of concepts, where such positions as the prototype theory, theory theory, or conceptual atomism are fiercely defended.⁴

- 4 A moment of reflection reveals that there is something wrong with this picture. How can an entity so instrumental to human thinking, which is “crucial to such psychological processes as categorisation, inference, memory, learning, and decision-making”,⁵ be so difficult to pinpoint from the ontological or structural perspective? How can something so indispensable be understood in such different ways? A powerful illusion must be at work here, one that safeguards the strong belief in the fundamental role of concepts despite theoretical difficulties in identifying and understanding their nature and place in human cognitive processes. How can one see through this illusion?
- 5 One may argue that the roots of the illusion are quite innocent, if not humble. It all begins with the way we learn language. Every parent must survive a long sequence of questions from their children; questions that inadvertently take the form “What is it?” or “What is it called?” “It’s a mango,” “this is a horse,” “that’s a brick,” “it’s green,” — the answers read. While human children learn their mother tongue in many ways, including through unconscious imitation, the conscious process almost always begins by *naming objects and their properties*. This is quite understandable. It is difficult to imagine learning (the first) language in any other way. In our environment we encounter only one kind of entity that enables stable perception, and hence relatively easy identification and re-identification. These are physical objects and (some of) their properties: mangos, bricks, horses, colours. Emotions, complex activities, or states of affair are much more difficult to pinpoint and then re-identify. And we need highly stable points of reference — a kind of anchor connecting our linguistic practice to reality — for language to work at all. As Ludwig Wittgenstein puts it, “The phenomenon of language rests on regularity, on agreement in acting. Here it is of the greatest importance that all of us, or the overwhelming number, agree on certain things. For example, I can be sure that the colour of this object will be called ‘green’ by most people who see it.”⁶
- 6 However, this is also the seed of the grand illusion. One gets the impression that everything there is to language, or at least the *fundamental aspect* of language, is the mysterious connection between particular words and the objects they designate. The impression is so strong that it found its way into philosophical reflection quite early in the history of the Western civilisation. What Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle did, was to model their view of the structure of the universe on taking the role of words (too) seriously. Socrates, as portrayed by Plato, was obsessed with the definitions of words such as justice or beauty. He believed that in each case there exists one right definition, and by formulating it one not only acquires a true picture of reality but is also compelled to act accordingly, i.e., in a morally sound way. Plato went even further, claiming that behind each of the terms one uses — ‘man’, ‘justice’, ‘beauty’, ‘triangle’ — there is an eternal and unchangeable idea that exists beyond time and space. Our task is to use the term in such a way, i.e., in line with such a definition, that it grasps the relevant idea. The things we perceive with our senses — people, just acts, beautiful things, or triangles — are mere reflections of the corresponding eternal ideas. Aristotle followed in the footsteps of his great predecessors, even if he changed the focus here or there. He also embraced the idea of essential definitions, which capture the forms of all

entities, whether a man or a triangle. Whatever can exist autonomously — a substance — is a combination of form and matter, the latter being the source of individual differences between the things that share the same form.⁷

- 7 In the subsequent history of philosophy, these essentialist views were often embraced, even if only modestly. It suffices to mention Locke, Kant, or Hegel to understand that the idea of concepts corresponding (in one way or another) to real objects (defined differently by various philosophers, but still real objects we encounter in our experience) has been dear to the luminaries of the Western thought. Of course, essentialist views were also contested or rejected by many thinkers. But even in these cases the claim that concepts are central to our cognitive activities faced little doubt. Even today it is quite difficult to argue that concepts are unimportant⁸ or even that they do not exist. It comes to us naturally to speak of concepts; it is almost impossible to question their key role. So, how can we undermine the importance of concepts? And is it reasonable to do so? Before answering those questions, it will help to first spend a few words on how language understanding is depicted in the contemporary cognitive sciences.

2 Mental simulations and language⁹

- 8 According to experimental research (and our everyday experience), people have the ability to imagine objects and events — to ‘represent them’ in their heads. The existence of this capacity may easily be explained in evolutionary terms: to be able to imaginatively ‘test’ potential solutions to encountered problems makes it possible to avoid errors at a relatively little cost. If I mentally simulate various methods of delivering a lecture in front of a demanding audience, I significantly increase the likelihood of giving a well-paced, interesting, and engaging talk. When one is to attend a difficult meeting with their employer, it is reasonable for them to first imagine how it will go, to prepare for what might happen.¹⁰
- 9 Even if we can offer a persuasive explanation of the emergence of the ability to mentally simulate, there remains the question of the mechanism behind it. In this context, we can gain insight from experiments based on the so-called Perky effect, i.e., the fact that using imagination interferes with visual perception. Why does such an effect occur? A natural explanation is that mental simulation takes advantage of (at least partially) the same neural circuitry active when actual visual perception takes place. This conclusion is reaffirmed by several recent experiments using brain imagining techniques.¹¹
- 10 An even more intriguing fact discovered by psychologists and neuroscientists is that when one hears, reads, or says a word, e.g., ‘hammer’, part of the same groups of neurones are activated as when one actually sees or imagines that thing. This is a profoundly important insight because it suggests that when processing (‘understanding’) language, we use (at least partially) the same brain circuits that constitute the mechanism behind perception, action, and imagination.
- 11 Consider the following example. One experiment involved the use of a screen and three buttons: a grey one, a black one, and a white one. Pressing and holding the grey button showed a sentence on the screen. If the sentence made sense, the subject was supposed to release the grey button and press the black one, which was located closer to the

subject; if the sentence did not make sense, the subject was to press the white button, which was located at a greater distance from the subject. It turned out that if a meaningful sentence — whether declarative or imperative — described an action involving movement towards the body, the subjects reacted faster than in the case of sentences describing motion in the opposite direction. This means that understanding the meaning of the sentences must have relied on performing an adequate simulation, and if the simulation was at odds with the motion that the subject was about to make (e.g., the sentence was about a movement away from the body and it made sense, so the button closer to the body had to be pressed), the reaction was slower.¹² We encounter here what may be called ‘the generalized Perky effect’: it pertains not only to visual perception and imagination, but embraces also other modalities (motor, olfactory, tactile, etc.).

- 12 Let me reemphasise the crucial point: numerous experimental studies, including those using neuroimaging as well as transcranial magnetic stimulation, together with observations of the behaviour of people with damage to particular regions of their brains, lead to the claim that people perform perceptual and motor simulation while they’re processing language. They do so by using the same parts of the brain they use to perceive the world and execute actions. Moreover, when specific aspects of embodied simulation are hindered, people have more trouble processing language about those specific aspects of perception or action. And finally, when brain regions dedicated to action or perception are damaged or temporarily taken offline, people have more trouble processing language about the specific perceptual or motor events they encode. Taken together, all this evidence makes for a compelling case that embodied simulation plays a functional role in language understanding.¹³
- 13 Let us now consider the consequences of the above enumerated facts. At the outset, it must be noted that there exists a continuity between pre-linguistic and linguistic understanding. We can understand the situation we face, recognise possible courses of action, or formulate predictions regarding future events thanks to our embodied knowledge of the world. When at an airport we spot a person behaving strangely, we become nervous. However, when we next see that person taking an anxiety pill, our emotions would likely transform into sympathy for our stressed co-passenger. We understand events in the world because we interact with the environment, thus forming a ‘conceptual scheme’ enabling us to navigate within the complex reality.¹⁴ We grasp imagined situations in the same way. In imagined situations, the embodied knowledge of the world is activated, providing means to predict the possible courses of action and what may happen. Finally, the same mechanism constitutes the ‘background’ to language processing. We understand linguistic utterances because we (usually unconsciously) mentally simulate their content.
- 14 Let us also observe that the described mechanism brings embodied knowledge into language comprehension. Our brains, trained through innumerable interactions with the environment, are prepared for (and “expect”) the co-occurrence of certain things or events. The fact that a certain object is red *eo ipso* means that it is not blue. To understand this, one needs no inference: the understanding in question is a derivative of the architecture of our brains and minds rather than a process of active/explicit reasoning.¹⁵ When someone tells us a story of a person who wanders through the Negev desert, we understand — again with no recourse to a chain of reasoning — that the person cannot reach Champs-Élysées in Paris within a couple of minutes.

- 15 Another important aspect of the language comprehension mechanism analysed here is the fact that mental simulations are multimodal. They are not limited to visual representations, but also include other modalities: auditory, tactile, motor, emotional, etc. This has far reaching consequences. In the traditional approach (as illustrated by Plato or Aristotle, as mentioned above), language is a tool for depicting the world. Because of that, nouns have a preeminent place in the structure of language, since they refer to objects. Objects constitute the fundamental substrate of the world, and whatever happens to them – that they move, are used to do something, or undergo a change – is, in a sense, derivative. However, if we process language thanks to multimodal mental simulations, this traditional picture is simply false. We understand that the word ‘hammer’ refers to an object in the same way as we understand that the word ‘drive’ refers to an action. I do not want to suggest that there are no differences between the perception, simulation, and hence, understanding of objects and actions. As I have already observed, objects are relatively stable (they are easy to identify and re-identify), whereas actions are not. However, given the above-described mechanism of language comprehension, this is not a critical difference, but it is consistent with the view that the primary function of language is *not* to describe the world.
- 16 Language serves numerous purposes, such as providing information regarding relevant facts or mental states, influencing others’ behaviour, attitudes, and emotions, or doing something together (from children’s play to complex technological undertakings). For example, it is easy to explain how the use of language generating mental simulations prepares an organism for action. If I tell someone to “Close the window!” and they – unconsciously – ‘play out’ a relevant simulation, the neural structures responsible for the execution of the action of closing the window will be activated. In this way, the organism has an easier passage from the verbal instruction to the actual behaviour. Meanwhile, if I tell someone who is about to close the window to “Open the door!”, it will interfere (as illustrated by many experiments)¹⁶ with the execution of the currently undertaken action.¹⁷

To repeat: there is a continuity between extra-linguistic and linguistic understanding. The comprehension of linguistic utterances takes advantage of the embodied knowledge of the world, and the functions of language are not limited to picturing reality. However, these conclusions apply only to (relatively) concrete language. The situation is different when we try to understand (interpret) abstract language, including legal language.

3 Between the concrete and the abstract

- 17 While it is relatively easy to explain what mental simulation of concrete linguistic expressions (‘drive a nail’, ‘Peter closed the door’, ‘tree’ or ‘yellow submarine’) consists in, it is much more difficult to grasp what imagining the content of abstract utterances, such as ‘legal person,’ ‘Hilbert’s space,’ ‘love,’ or even ‘to commit a crime,’ amounts to. Even if expressions such as ‘Riemann’s zeta function’ or ‘strict liability’ may cause some conscious or unconscious mental simulations, it is doubtful that they are similar in differing English speakers.
- 18 Let us observe that the above-mentioned abstract expressions are quite different.¹⁸ ‘Legal person’, ‘human being’, ‘crime’ or ‘entity’ are names referring to classes of objects or events. ‘Legal person’ is every organisation that fulfils the conditions set forth in the relevant statutes; and a ‘human being,’ at least according to Aristotle, is

every rational animal. ‘Love,’ like ‘justice,’ ‘beauty,’ or ‘economic efficiency,’ are concepts referring to no concrete object in spacetime; one can argue that they refer to some states of affairs, but there seems to be something artificial in this way of speaking. ‘Hilbert’s space,’ ‘Mandelbrot’s set,’ ‘imaginary number,’ and other mathematical concepts are a different case. They refer neither to objects, physical events, nor states of affairs. A Platonic philosopher would say that they name mathematical structures, which exist independent of the physical realm; a constructivist would argue that they are our common mental constructions; and a nominalist would consider them mere linguistic entities, which refer to nothing in the extra-linguistic reality.

- 19 In addition to this heterogeneity, abstraction has one more interesting feature: it is gradual. Indeed, even the most concrete linguistic expression (apart from proper names) is connected to some measure of abstraction. Let us consider the name ‘the author of *Waverley*’. Even though this description can serve to univocally identify a concrete person — sir Walter Scott — it is abstract in the sense that it ignores infinitely many features of the actual Scott. ‘The author of *Waverley*’ is, at the same time, more concrete than ‘human being,’ which in turn is more concrete than ‘animal,’ which is more concrete than ‘a living organism,’ which is more concrete than ‘entity’. Similarly, the sequence of mathematical concepts: ‘equilateral triangle’ — ‘triangle’ — ‘plane figure’ — ‘geometrical object’, is ordered from the least to the most abstract.
- 20 These two properties of abstract expressions — heterogeneity and gradation — constitute an intriguing puzzle, which suggests that it is impossible to explain the generation and understanding of abstract concepts with recourse to one simple mechanism. At the same time, the two properties may also guide our search for an acceptable solution to the puzzle. From this perspective, it seems that one can speak of (at least) three different but interconnected ways of creating abstract concepts. The first is generalisation: when we have a concept referring to a class of objects — e.g., apples — by ‘disregarding’ some features of apples, we can create a more general concept (e.g., of fruits). Let us further observe that we do not necessarily begin with the most concrete concepts, but with those that (in the given natural and cultural environment) are the most useful. For example, the name of an apple cultivar such as ‘Jonathan’ is more concrete than ‘apple’; however, mothers first teach their children to distinguish between apples and other kinds of fruit, and only after that (if at all) explain what apples cultivars are.¹⁹
- 21 The second method of generating abstract concepts may be called ‘structural mapping’. Conceptual metaphors are a good example here. A metaphor is a mapping of the inferential structure from a more concrete domain (e.g., pertaining to war) to a more abstract domain (e.g., to speak of argumentation in terms of attacking arguments, argumentative strategies, or winning an argument).²⁰ Various studies show that the processing of metaphorical language is based, at least to a certain degree, on mental simulations.²¹
- 22 It may further be speculated that there are concept generating mechanisms that have nothing to do with mental simulations: everything happens at the level of linguistic symbols. For example, it is quite likely that non-Euclidean geometries were created in this way. Lobaczewsky and Bolyai simply considered what would happen if Euclid’s fifth postulate of was negated. I do not want to suggest that their thinking on the matter involved no mental simulations whatsoever, but these simulations must have been

highly idiosyncratic. Moreover, they do not constitute a condition of understanding non-Euclidean geometries. Let us further note that this way of creating abstract objects requires a relevant theoretical framework: non-Euclidean geometries were developed against the background of Euclidean geometry. There was no *creatio ex nihilo* here, but a re-modelling of the existing conceptual structure.

- 23 The above considerations make it possible to better understand the gradual nature of abstraction. From this perspective, linguistic expressions form a hierarchy. Those more concrete are strictly connected to mental simulations. When one says ‘hammer,’ ‘apple,’ ‘grasp,’ or ‘drives a nail,’ one understands these utterances through (usually unconscious) mental simulation of their content. However, when we move higher on the scale of abstraction, the role of mental simulation decreases and formal relationships between concepts and entire theories come to the fore. A metaphor, which already leads us into the domain of abstraction, remains connected to the embodied schemes developed in interactions with the environment. The creation of purely theoretical constructions, however, such as non-Euclidean geometry (not to mention even more abstract mathematical objects), is independent of any particular mental simulation. We understand them not because we can imagine their content but because we are able to place them within a broader theoretical framework.
- 24 Thus, understanding has a double, concrete-abstract nature. On the one hand, we understand linguistic utterances, because we can mentally simulate their content. From this viewpoint, understanding is embodied, since it is deeply rooted in the motor and perceptual schemes developed in our brains during our interactions with the environment. On the other hand, linguistic expressions become meaningful within the context of broader theoretical structures. It is a space where new abstract constructions may be developed with no recourse to embodied schemes. One can venture to say that theories constitute a kind of scaffolding that helps us move from one concrete perception or action to another. This is, ostensibly, what scientific theories do — they link one concrete observation (of initial conditions) to another concrete observation (the predicted outcome). But other kinds of theories do the same thing. Our folk understanding of human action links particular circumstances (i.e., reasons for doing something) to concrete behaviour (the action undertaken “because” of some reasons). From this perspective, the two fundamental ways of language understanding — through mental simulations and through theoretical constructs — are not isolated mechanisms that have nothing to do with one another. Rather, they are two extremes of a spectrum.²²
- 25 While sketching the picture of language understanding emerging from contemporary cognitive science — more precisely, from the embodied mind paradigm — I have at times spoken as if there were concepts playing a crucial role in our cognitive activities. This is, ultimately, a very common idiom among cognitive scientists, and hence it is difficult to present their views without making recourse to concepts. But let us now try a different route and ask whether the picture sketched above requires concepts as pivotal elements in the mechanism of perception and understanding.

4 The disenchantment of concepts

- 26 Against the backdrop of the embodied theory of language comprehension sketched above, one may argue that there exist concrete concepts (those firmly rooted in mental

simulations), abstract concepts (those at the other side of the spectrum, and not associated with particular patterns of mental simulations, but rather definable through the theoretical constructions in which they are embedded), and many in-between. Let us, however, *ignore* what lies in-between for the time being, since it only makes the picture more complicated, and concentrate on the cases closer to the two ends of the spectrum.

- 27 From this perspective, one may argue that there indeed are concrete concepts, such as ‘a horse,’ ‘blue,’ or ‘running’. In interactions with the environment, humans acquire neural activation patterns associated with perceiving or doing something (e.g., seeing a horse, or executing or observing an action such as riding a bike, etc.). These patterns are then reused for imagining the relevant things or events. Moreover, our interactions also include using language, and hence the use of a certain language expression (e.g., “This is a horse,” “The t-shirt is blue,” “John is running the New York marathon,” etc.) becomes associated with the relevant, co-occurring activation pattern. One may also argue that since the perception of external objects, as opposed to actions or inner states such as emotions, is quite stable, the relevant patterns for the identification of external objects and their properties are relatively more stable and precise. They are like firm anchors, which keep the entire edifice of language in place. This, of course, explains the way humans acquire language, and the crucial role of “naming-by-ostension” in particular.
- 28 At this level, it is easy to understand why some philosophers insist that concepts are mental representations. If, indeed, the mechanism of mental simulations is key to the processing of concrete concepts, the relevant neural activation patterns constitute a brain-level foundation of concepts as mental representations. Arguably, however, one may also insist that (concrete) concepts are *abilities*. Ultimately, the mechanism of relevant activation patterns enables one to recognise an object, a property of an object, or an action. On the other hand, it would be extremely difficult to defend the view that concepts are *abstract objects*: there is nothing abstract in the organisation of neural networks in the human brain, and since it is the very mechanism that helps us to *represent* reality, as well as provides us with the *ability* to recognise what we perceive, one is entitled to claim that concepts are mental representations or abilities but not that they are abstract entities. Another important observation is that at the contemplated level, the claim that concepts *precede* or (at the very least) are *independent of* language is fully defensible. Although using the same language decisively helps shape the relevant activation patterns in the brains of the members of the same language community in a similar way, some such patterns would form even without the presence of language.
- 29 At the level of abstract concepts, the situation is quite different. Although some mental simulations may be involved in processing them, they form no stable patterns. Rather, abstract concepts are not directly rooted in the activation patterns that enable mental simulation; they are, in a way, “disembodied”. They acquire their function from the place they occupy in a theoretical construction. As such, they are only parts of a theoretical scaffolding that helps us move from one concrete perception or action to another.
- 30 It may be difficult to see this because of two facts. The first is that we tend to understand what a theory is in a very particular way. Theories, we think, are what scientists construct, find their way into textbooks, and are taught in schools and

universities. But this is quite misleading. Humans construct theories on daily basis. A theory is simply a set of interconnected sentences that describe (and explain) a given aspect of experience. Special relativity is a theory, but a narrative that uncovers the reasons for a neighbour's behaviour is also a theory. Even a single sentence — e.g., that people should not be egoists — is a theory.

- 31 The second fact making it difficult to grasp the idea that (abstract) concepts are embedded in theories is that concepts (or, more precisely, linguistic expressions we take as designating concepts) usually feature in many, often mutually inconsistent, theories. “Justice” is a part of conceptions based on the claim that just acts are impartial acts, but is also embedded in theories driven by the idea of mutual advantage.²³ Moreover, during the inculturation process, humans become accustomed to various versions of those theories. A child may be informed by their parents that to act in a just way one should not think only about oneself; a secondary-level school student may be instructed that one should choose those courses of action that are (most) beneficial for the society, and think through the principle of the greatest happiness for the highest number of people. A philosophy major, who dives into the works of Hume and Bentham and becomes accustomed with the corresponding huge secondary literature, will learn the strengths and weaknesses of the justice-as-mutual-advantage approach to morality in much more detail. It is not surprising that these people — a child, a secondary school student, and a philosophy major — will use the word ‘justice’ in quite different ways. This shows that any attempt to *uncover* the meaning of the concept of justice from the way people use the word is destined to fail. True, there are some stable patterns in the use of words pertaining to abstract concepts, but the mechanism behind such regularities is quite different than in the case of concrete concepts. Here lies the illusion: because of the way the latter function, we have an incorrect picture of the functioning of the former.
- 32 One can go even further and argue that abstract concepts — as used by individual people in concrete situations — are fully idiosyncratic. Usually, people just use certain words (such as “justice” or “animal”) and do not have any particular theory of what it means for an action to be just or a creature to be considered an animal. When asked about their understanding of the given word, they *construct* such a theory on the spot. However, the construction is culturally conditioned through education, or through what people have heard or read and are able to recall. This explains why such constructions are similar across a given community; but this also shows why and how idiosyncratic they are.
- 33 The above considerations show that it is quite difficult to claim that abstract concepts are mental representations. In contradistinction to concrete concepts, which — through the mechanism of mental simulation — do capture some invariant aspects of the perceived reality²⁴ and as such may be said to *mentally represent* something, abstract concepts — if they can be said to exist at all — are embedded in theories, i.e., they are *outside* of one's mind. Naturally, the theories are somehow processed by the human mind, so that at any given time there is an idiosyncratic neural and/or mental substrate of an abstract concept. However, it would be strange to say that it *represents* anything.
- 34 Similarly, it would be difficult to substantiate the claim that abstract concepts — as embedded in theories — are *abilities*. It is true that our mental architecture enables us to use such expressions as ‘value added tax,’ ‘justice,’ or ‘Hilbert's space’ and thus we indeed have an *ability* to identify certain things or states of affairs as belonging to an

abstract category or instantiating an abstract relation. However, to say that it is an ability to apply an abstract concept would be possible only by embracing a rather extreme form of behaviourism. It is true that when presented with a relevant stimulus, people are able to respond by using such words as ‘table,’ ‘blue,’ ‘justice,’ or ‘icosahedron,’ but it may be said that it is *the same* ability only if one treated the mind as a ‘black box,’ the workings of which are unknown. Meanwhile, we have strong reasons to assume that the mechanism leading to the correct application of ‘table’ or ‘blue’ is quite different from what enables us to speak of justice or icosahedrons. But if these mechanisms are so different, are we justified in saying that in all four cases we are dealing with the same phenomenon, i.e., with concepts? I think not.

- 35 It may seem that when speaking of abstract concepts, one is entitled to claim that they are *abstract entities*. By definition, abstract entities are *outside our minds*: we can somehow grasp them as illustrated by our ability to contemplate paradigmatic abstract entities, e.g., mathematical objects. Indeed, given the proper metaphysical inclination, one may argue that abstract concepts are entities of the kind considered here. However, one must remember that this is a strong ontological claim, one that comes with additional complications. First, if abstract concepts were considered abstract entities, such different things as ‘justice,’ ‘irrational number,’ and ‘material object,’ would populate the world of independently existing abstractions. Second, given our considerations so far, it would be difficult to say the same of concrete objects (e.g., “table” or “blue”), which seem to deserve the tag of ‘mental representations’. Finally, if abstract concepts were abstract entities, one would need to answer a tough epistemological question: how is the embodied human mind capable of grasping and contemplating abstract objects? We know — more or less — what it means to use language, put forward hypotheses, construct theories, and test and discuss them. But what does the contemplation of one isolated abstract concept look like? How do we do the trick of conceptualizing it? When considering these questions, the level of theoretical complication becomes alarmingly high.
- 36 The simple reaction to those considerations is to say that it is high time to lift the illusion surrounding abstract concepts. Speaking of them is still allowed in that ultimately, one cannot decree that some common uses of language are prohibited, but our understanding of what we are talking about should change. When dealing with abstract concepts one is not contemplating complex mental representations or mysterious abstract entities. In fact, due to the long tradition of treating abstract concepts as something crucial to philosophical reflection, a tradition firmly anchored in the grand illusion I described above, it only *seems* that we are dealing with concepts, when in reality we are doing something else. But what is it?

5 Popper’s neglected argument

- 37 Karl Popper was one of the greatest philosophers of the 20th century. He is, however, usually regarded primarily as a great as a philosopher of science and a political philosopher, who authored *The Open Society and its Enemies*. We might even venture to say that Popper’s contributions outside the philosophy of science and political philosophy have been more or less systematically ignored. Meanwhile, his insights regarding epistemology and ontology — always anchored in what science has to say,

but also based on a real talent for observation — are at least worth considering, if not embracing.

A case in point is what he has to say about concepts and meaning. In his intellectual autobiography, *The Unended Quest*, Popper argues that “behind the classical problem of universal words and their meaning (or sense, or denotation) there loomed a deeper and more important problem: the problem of universal laws and their truth; that is, the problem of regularities.”²⁵ To better grasp what lies behind this claim, he urges us to consider the

<p>IDEAS <i>that is</i></p>	
<p>DESIGNATIONS OF TERMS OR CONCEPTS</p>	<p>STATEMENTS OF PROPOSITIONS OF THEORIES</p>
<p><i>may be formulated in</i></p>	
<p>WORDS</p>	<p>ASSERTIONS</p>
<p><i>which may be</i></p>	
<p>MEANINGFUL</p>	<p>TRUE</p>
<p><i>and their</i></p>	
<p>MEANING</p>	<p>TRUTH</p>
<p><i>may be reduced, by way of</i></p>	
<p>DEFINITIONS</p>	<p>DERIVATIONS</p>
<p><i>to that of</i></p>	
<p>UNDEFINED CONCEPTS</p>	<p>PRIMITIVE PROPOSITIONS</p>
<p><i>the attempt to establish (rather than reduce) by these means their</i></p>	
<p>MEANING</p>	<p>TRUTH</p>
<p><i>leads to an infinite regress</i></p>	

following table:²⁶

- 38 He further claims that “in spite of the perfect logical analogy between the left and the right sides of this table, the left-hand side is philosophically unimportant, while the right-hand side is philosophically all-important.”²⁷ It follows that philosophers who overemphasise the importance of analysing the meaning of words or inquiries into the nature and function of concepts are completely wrong. As Popper argues, “In matters of the intellect, the only things worth striving for are true theories, or theories which come near to the truth — at any rate nearer than some other (competing) theory, for example an older one.”²⁸ Investigating the meaning of words or concepts will not lead us far. One may argue that even if our main goal is to construct, assess, and modify (or reject) theories, concepts are still important, since they are the building-blocks of statements, which, in turn, are the bricks from which any theory is constructed. Popper insists, however, that this view is misleading. In fact, it is better to say that “the relationship between a theory (or a statement) and the words used in its formulation is in several ways analogous to that between written words and the letters used in writing them down.”²⁹
- 39 This is a surprising and strong thesis. We have been told by our parents and teachers that to understand a sentence we need to know the meanings of the expressions that make up the sentence. We know what one intends to convey while saying the “The

table is brown” or “There is no justice when there is no mutual advantage”, because we know what “table” and “brown” and “justice” mean. According to Popper, this is not as things really are. He provides several intriguing arguments to substantiate his thesis, but given the framework I presented above, there is no need to repeat them here. Popper’s claim is much easier to understand and justify when we take our framework into account. The linguistic expressions we use are more or less associated with neural activation patterns, which are shaped by our experiences and serve to navigate the world but also carry out mental simulations. There are a rich variety of words or linguistic expressions well-rooted in the activation patterns and processed through mental simulations. Some of them are terms related to objects in the world (or their properties), e.g., “table” or “brown,”, but others refer to actions or some arrangements of things, e.g., “running” or “road crossing”. If language was limited to such expressions, the naive view that the meaning of a sentence is determined by the meaning of its constituent parts (words, expressions, concepts) would be understandable even if a bit simplified. However, there are also more abstract expressions, which are not generally directly connected to any regular simulation patterns, but are meaningful because they are elements of theories.

- 40 From this perspective, one may argue that Popper is at the same time both wrong and right. He is wrong in relation to *some* expressions — those more concrete and processed through mental simulations —, which seem to function in the fashion depicted in the traditional conception: we need to know their meaning to understand a sentence in which they appear. But he is also right when more abstract expressions — those embedded in theories — are considered. Indeed, they seem to have no meaning outside of a theory. To accept this dualistic stance, however, would mean that one has completely missed the crux of Popper’s argument. Popper does *not* claim that words have no meaning; to the contrary, even from his table it is obvious that speaking of concepts and meanings is an acceptable — or at least a possible — idiom. He does not even deny that “we must understand words in order to understand a theory.”³⁰ It is obvious, after all, that we can provide definitions of the expressions we use, both concrete and abstract. If one is unable to provide such definitions of terms appearing in a theory, say, of some key terms of tax law, one cannot be said to understand tax law.
- 41 Popper’s argument aims elsewhere. He believes that the sole analysis of concepts or how particular words are used is not a procedure which — as such — may help us identify or solve problems, e.g., explain physical phenomena, introduce legal regulations, or decide what to eat for breakfast. No problem has ever been solved in this way, and there is a reason for that. When dealing with a problem, we need a *theory* — even if it is only a poor excuse for the kind of theories we know from science — like a simple sentence that urges us not to be egoists. No amount of analytical effort aimed at scrutinising the meaning of the term ‘egoist’ would help us establish whether we should indeed do our best not to act in an egoistic way. However, one may insist that such an analysis can make our theory more precise. As a consequence, it will be easier for us to distinguish between egoistic and non-egoistic acts. The problem is that whether a greater level of precision is needed is always dictated by a problem one encounters while applying a theory. Thus, any elucidation of a concept is, in fact, a function of a revision of a theory. As Popper observes, precision for precision’s sake is not a goal worth pursuing. Our theories should be as precise as needed to solve our

problems. For instance, an elaborate analysis of the concept of egoism is of little value for a child we instruct in basic rules of human interaction.

- 42 To shed more light on how Popper sees human problem-solving activities, let us consider the following passage, where he explains how we deal with the abstract:
- we may understand it (...) as an active process. In order to understand a difficult Latin sentence, we have to construe it: to see how it is made, and to re-construct it, to re-make it. In order to understand a problem, we have to try at least some of the more obvious solutions, and to discover that they fail; thus we rediscover that there is a difficulty – a problem. In order to understand a theory, we have first to understand the problem which the theory was designed to solve, and to see whether the theory does better than do any of the more obvious solutions. (...) In all these cases the understanding becomes ‘intuitive’ when we have acquired the feeling that we can do the work of reconstruction at will, at any time.³¹
- 43 These observations have far-reaching consequences. What Popper shows is that when we are dealing with abstraction, our actual activities have little to do with analysing concepts. To re-make a difficult Latin sentence does not amount to scrutinising the meaning of its constituent expressions. This may help but it is not sufficient. We need to grasp the grammatical structure of the sentence. We need to try out different translations and see how they fit together with the immediate context of the sentence as well as what we know of the Romans’ general worldview. Understanding does not come from grasping the meanings of isolated words or concepts, which somehow add up to form a sentence or an entire theory. If so, it is not reasonable to concentrate on such individual concepts; more important is a theory that serves to solve a problem one has encountered.
- 44 Popper’s argument comes with a normative conclusion: he urges us to do one thing (work with theories) rather than another (analyse concepts and meanings). But his insightful observations may also be read in a different way. What Popper shows is that when one is working with a problem, one *in fact* works through creating, assessing, and modifying theories, even if it may *seem* that one is doing conceptual analysis. We disguise our real activity – theory-construction – in the linguistic clothes of an idiom that puts concepts in the spotlight. But this is yet another illusion.

6 The legal philosophy of Monsieur Joubert

- 45 Conceptual analysis is arguably the fundamental method of jurisprudence, at least within the paradigm of analytical jurisprudence, which first originated in the Anglophone world but has since spread all over the world. It would be quite difficult to list even a small fraction of the important books and papers that adopt this approach. It is, in other words, difficult to imagine legal theory and philosophy of law even remotely resembling its current state without the benefits of conceptual analysis. Or rather, so it seems.
- 46 Methodological reflection is not the focus of analytical legal philosophers. However, such reflection does exist and is sometimes critical of what is perceived as the basic intellectual tools used in this paradigm. A case in point is Andrei Marmor’s *Farewell to Conceptual Analysis (in Jurisprudence)*, a paper that opens with a surprising if not revolutionary claim: “Analytical legal philosophy is not an exercise in conceptual analysis.”³² Marmor goes on to say that when we look at the major works in analytical jurisprudence, most notably H.L.A. Hart’s *The Concept of Law*,³³ we do not find many

arguments employing conceptual analysis. Hart's goal, as well as (presumably) other analytic legal philosophers, especially those who label themselves "legal positivists", is to develop a *reductionist* theory of law. And indeed, when one carefully reads Hart's *opus magnum*, it transpires that he strives to show — mainly by recourse to the ideas of external and internal points of view — that law can and should be largely seen as a sociological phenomenon, i.e., it is reducible (in a sense of "reduction" understood along the lines of the relation of supervenience or grounding) to empirical phenomena.

- 47 Marmor rightly observes that conceptual analysis may help, and has helped, in this endeavour but only in a limited way. Hart's attempt should be seen as primarily an exercise in theory-construction. Marmor assumes further that conceptual analysis — or at least the procedure deserving this label — consists in scrutinising "the ways in which words function in our actual language games, which must be based on observation of linguistic practices and prevailing linguistic intuitions."³⁴ This is a definition of the so-called Oxford-style analysis, a method used widely by such philosophers as J.L. Austin and Gilbert Ryle. Marmor believes that it is the only way conceptual analysis may be understood, since no analysis should lead to the *revision* of how concepts function; and the only way to grasp how they are actually used is to look at existing linguistic practice.
- 48 It has been argued, however, that there are other approaches to conceptual analysis; methods, which, even if they may lead to a kind of revision of the conceptual scheme, seem to be deserving of the name.³⁵ One notable example is the so-called Canberra-style analysis.³⁶ This method takes advantage of the procedure known as Ramsification, which consists in formulating a Ramsey sentence for the given theory. By formulating a Ramsey sentence, one eliminates theoretical (i.e., non-observational) predicates from a theory by replacing them with a (second-order) variable ranging over predicates. For instance, instead of saying that gravitation makes objects fall, one may replace 'gravitation', a non-observable property, with a second-order variable preceded by an existential quantifier and claim that "There exists such an X that X causes objects to fall".
- 49 What do we get by doing so? Observe that by putting together a Ramsey sentence for a theory T (i.e., a conjunction of all the sentences belonging to T in which non-observational predicates have been replaced by variables preceded by an existential quantifier), one gets a (logically weaker) theory expressed in observational terms only. There are no "purely theoretical" terms there; the places in the theory's structure where they originally appeared are "marked" by second order variables. This enables one to identify what the "theoretical layer" of a given theory consists in, or what has been added to observations as a theoretical explanation. There are several advantages to utilising this procedure, such as the possibility to formulate an alternative theoretical structure on the basis of the same observational data or exposing relations between different theoretical terms.
- 50 Philosophers who proclaim themselves the representatives of the Canberra approach believe that such a procedure may also be used to investigate issues that do not necessarily come with a well-formulated theory, e.g., our understanding of the way the mind works. To do so, one needs to first uncover the so-called platitudes, i.e., beliefs about a given subject that are widely held in a community. For example, it is reasonable to assume that most people believe that to act in a given way one first needs to form an intention. Intention is not observable. Thus, the "theory" saying that intentions cause

action may be Ramsified: “There exists an X such that X causes action”. Now, once one has gotten rid of the troublesome theoretical baggage, they may inquire into the real nature of X. A naturalistically inclined philosopher may in this way end up with the claim that what people call intentions are in fact particular activations of the neural networks in our brains. There is no real revision of the way we use the word “intention”. Rather, our philosopher discovers what people are talking about while speaking of intentions.

51 Is this *really* conceptual analysis? One needs to be careful here. Indeed, the entire procedure revolves around eliminating and introducing *terms* from and into a theory. But one does *not* contemplate any concepts as such. What is done here, is the transformation of entire theories (within the process of Ramsification); there is also the question of how to understand the theory or how it relates to reality. Of course, one may insist that this is conceptual analysis, but it is conceptual only insofar as playing with terms (concepts) helps us better understand or improve our theories! (I leave aside the question of whether this type of analysis may indeed help us do those things. I suppose a physicist would be very much perplexed when presented with a Canberra style analysis of the general theory of relativity or some other fundamental physical theory. They would see no point — no real advantage — in making such a great intellectual effort to achieve so little).

52 It may also be surprising and insightful to consider what may count as a Canberra style analysis in the domain of legal philosophy. Arguably, many of the major contributions to the field can be reconstructed as partially taking advantage of this type of analysis. For example, it seems possible to paraphrase Hart’s analysis in *The Concept of Law* as aiming at uncovering the platitudes people have in relation to law, since Hart proceeds by scrutinizing linguistic intuitions pertaining to the use of such words as “law,” “liability,” or “obligation”. Consider the following passage:

If it were true that the statement that a person had an obligation meant that he was likely to suffer in the event of disobedience, it would be a contradiction to say that he had an obligation, e.g. to report for military service but that, owing to the fact that he had escaped from the jurisdiction, or had successfully bribed the police or the court, there was not the slightest chance of his being caught or made to suffer. In fact, there is no contradiction in saying this, and such statements are often made and understood.³⁷

53 What Hart captures here is a linguistic fact that competent English users have no trouble saying that someone may have an obligation even if they are not punished for their failure to fulfil it. This, in turn, is an expression of a platitude (a commonly held belief) that obligations cannot be understood merely in terms of regularities in social relations. A sufficiently rich collection of such platitudes enables Hart to uncover the theoretical structure of a “folk” view of the law (in other words, the “folk” theory of law), and hence the place of theoretical concepts such as “law” or “obligation” in relation to some observational (empirical) facts. For example, he claims that one can speak of the existence of social rules (including legal ones) only when two observational criteria are jointly fulfilled: one can observe regularities in people’s behaviour (external point of view) as well as the expression of some special attitudes towards particular courses of action (internal point of view). At this juncture, Hart does not follow the precepts of the Canberra style analysis but enriches the identified theoretical level of the folk account of the law by introducing the concepts of primary and secondary rules and their union.

- 54 I am aware that the above presented paraphrase of Hart's argument may seem far-fetched. However, the point of the exercise is not to claim that Hart was a representative of the Canberra style analysis *avant la lettre*. Rather, to emphasize again, Hart is not primarily concerned with *concepts* but with *theories*. He elucidates concepts such as "law," "obligation," or "liability" only to the extent that he clarifies their place and role in a theory that describes human legal practices. A concept taken in isolation, outside of a theory within which it is embedded, is ultimately meaningless. One may think otherwise only when blind to the actual role theories play in our cognitive efforts. It is true that various definitions of law can be provided that the concept itself can be elucidated, but all such endeavours are possible only because there is an explicitly expressed or implicitly held *theory* of law-related practices in the background.
- 55 If this is even roughly true, then legal philosophers – even if they believe they are doing conceptual analysis – are doing something different. They are formulating theories, paraphrasing them, comparing them to alternatives, modifying and rejecting them. Like Moliere's Monsieur Jourdain, they have been speaking in prose all their lives without realising it. But they could have done nothing else. The poetry of conceptual analysis is a beautiful and captivating illusion. It's time to see through it and work a bit on the quality and style of our prose.

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NOTES

1. For an overview see Hage & Pfordten 2009 and the literature cited therein.
2. As the Reader will quickly realize, the argument I offer here pertains to all concept, not just legal ones. Only the final section of the paper is focused exclusively on legal discourse. There are several reasons behind this (surprising, I admit) argumentation structure. First, I speak here mainly to legal philosophers, and hence it is only reasonable to highlight the consequences of my observations for the understanding of legal concepts. Second, it seems that the importance of concepts is particularly stressed in legal theory and philosophy (of course, it is my subjective assessment, but I see no similar level of insistence on analysing concepts in any other field of philosophical reflection). Third, I do not believe that legal concepts have any highly peculiar features distinguishing them from other concepts – they are processed through the same cognitive mechanism as any other concept. In relation to this claim cf. Brožek 2019.
3. Margolis & Laurence 2023.
4. Cf. Margolis & Laurence 2023.
5. Margolis & Laurence 2023.
6. Wittgenstein 1998: §342.
7. A good introduction to the ontological views of Plato and Aristotle can be found in Reale 1990. A critical assessment of those theories is presented in Popper 2020. Of

course, no secondary literature can replace reading Plato's original dialogues or Aristotle's treatises.

8. Cf. Machery 2009, where the author forcefully argues that one should abandon speaking of concepts in the theoretical and experimental psychology, since this idiom only generates confusion.

9. The following two sections are a modification of a part of Brożek 2020.

10. Brożek 2016: 111 ff.

11. Cf. Bergen 2012: 73 ff.

12. Bergen 2012: 81 ff.

13. Bergen 2012: 238.

14. Cf. Churchland 2012: *passim*.

15. Cf. Churchland 2012: 35 ff.

16. Cf. Jeannerod 2001: S103–S109.

17. Cf. Brożek 2016.

18. Cf. Anglelelli 2004.

19. Cf. Rosch 1978: 6–7.

20. Cf. Lakoff & Johnson 1999: *passim*.

21. Cf. Bergen 2012: 195 ff.

22. See also Salmon 1990.

23. Cf. Załuski 2006.

24. Cf. Churchland 2012.

25. Popper 2005: 16.

26. Popper 2005: 18.

27. Popper 2005: 18.

28. Popper 2005: 19.

29. Popper 2005: 20.

30. Popper 2005: 20.

31. Popper & Eccles 1977: 44–45.

32. Marmor 2013.

33. Hart 1994.

34. Marmor 2013: 212.

35. Cf. Banaś & Gołba: 2017.

36. Cf. Nolan 2010.

37. Hart 1994: 84.

ABSTRACTS

The argument presented in the paper revolves around the question of the existence of legal concepts. It is widely assumed that concepts are essential in reasoning in general, and legal reasoning in particular. Meanwhile, it is surprisingly difficult to grasp and explain the nature and structure of concepts. There are several, often incompatible, theories of concepts. From this perspective, it is reasonable to ask whether concepts are indeed so instrumental in legal thinking. In this context, much insight may be gained by analysing recent advancements in the cognitive sciences, especially within the so-called embodied mind paradigm. Against this background I argue that while one is entitled to speak of the existence of concepts, they would gain more understanding and solve pressing problems when ignoring legal concepts (whatever they are taken to be) and instead concentrating on constructing, revising, comparing and applying theories. I further claim that – despite appearances – working with theories is exactly what legal scholars do.

Odčaranje pravnih pojmov. Prispevek se osredotoča na vprašanje obstoja pravnih pojmov. Splošno razširjeno je prepričanje, da so pojmi bistveni za razmišljanje nasploh, še posebej pa za pravno mišljenje. Kljub temu je presenetljivo težko razumeti in pojasniti naravo in strukturo pojmov. Obstaja več, pogosto med seboj nezdržljivih teorij o pojmi. S tega vidika je smiselno postaviti vprašanje, ali so pojmi res tako ključni za pravno mišljenje. Pomemben vpogled nam v tem kontekstu ponuja razčlemba nedavnih dosežkov na področju kognitivnih znanosti, zlasti znotraj t. i. paradigme utelešenega uma. Avtor prispevka na osnovi teh dosežkov trdi, da lahko kljub upravičenosti govora o obstoju pojmov pridobimo več razumevanja in rešitev za pereče probleme, če pravne pojme (ne glede na to, kako jih razumemo) odmislimo in se namesto tega osredotočimo na snovanje, preoblikovanje, primerjavo in uporabo teorij. Ob tem še poudarja, da – kljub videzu – prav to v resnici počnejo pravni učenjaki.

INDEX

Keywords: legal concepts, conceptual analysis, Canberra Plan, legal language, legal reasoning, abstraction in law, theory construction

motslessl pravni pojmi, pojmovna analiza, Canberrski načrt, pravni jezik, pravno sklepanje, abstrakcija v pravu, oblikovanje teorij

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